

First report of a Recent occurrence of *Scalargonoba* (Gastropoda: Heterobranchia) in the Atlantic Ocean

Primera cita de una ocurrencia actual de *Scalargonoba* (Gastropoda: Heterobranchia) en el Océano Atlántico

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ABSTRACT

A new species collected off Madeira in 100-130 m water depth is described in the genus *Scalargonoba* Powell, 1927, so far only reported from Australia and New Zealand. The genus *Camporellina* Bertolaso & Palazzi, 1997, described from the Italian Pliocene, is regarded as a synonym of *Scalargonoba*. The genus is placed in the family Cimidae Warén, 1993 following current literature, and not in Eulimidae as had been assumed from misreading of published statements.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie recolectada frente a Madeira en una profundidad de 100-130 m, en el género *Scalargonoba* Powell, 1927 que se conocía hasta ahora solamente en Australia y Nueva Zelanda. El género *Camporellina* Bertolaso & Palazzi, 1997, descrito del Plioceno italiano, se considera sinónimo de *Scalargonoba*. El género se asigna a la familia Cimidae Warén, 1993 de acuerdo con la literatura actual, y no a Eulimidae, como se había asumido a partir de una interpretación errónea de las opiniones publicadas.

KEY WORDS: Relict species, Tofanellidae, Cimidae, Madeira.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Especie relict, Tofanellidae, Cimidae, Madeira.

INTRODUCTION

Minute micromolluscs in the size range of ca. 1 mm are still a challenge in completing faunal inventories, as they are commonly lost through sieving in meshes above 0.5 or 1 mm. This report regards an unusual species which was collected off Madeira and stored for many years in an unsorted sample. It is considered the first record

of the genus *Scalargonoba* Powell, 1927, so far known only from Australasia, in the Atlantic Ocean. A Pliocene fossil from Italy is also compared and reassessed.

The molluscan fauna of Madeira is nowadays comparatively well-known, summarized in SEGERS *ET AL.* (2009), albeit new additions are still possible.

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MATERIAL AND METHODS

From 12 to 22 July 1966, R/V “Jean Charcot” on her maiden biological cruise (expedition leaders J.-M. Pérès and J. Vacelet of Station Marine d’Endoume), explored the area around Madeira with 64 stations including plankton tows, dredging, sediment sampling with a grab, intertidal coastal and

diving collections. So far, the material has not been globally studied and only scattered taxonomic publications mention this material. Sediment samples still unsorted in MNHN were sieved on 5mm, 1mm and 0.5 mm sieves and sorted for micromolluscs. Specimens were cleaned with mild sonication, mounted on a stub and coated with gold for SEM observation.

RESULTS

Genus *Scalaronoba* Powell, 1927

Scalaronoba madeirensis n. sp.

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Type material – *Holotype*: MADEIRA • 1 sh. (Fig. 1 A, B); off Desertas Is.; 32°28.7'N, 16° 39.7' W; 100 130 m; 18 Jul. 1966; leg. H. Zibrowius; R/V *Jean Charcot*, Zarco sta. 46; MNHN IM 2000 28954. *Paratypes*: MADEIRA • 5 sh. (Fig. 1 C); same data as for holotype; MNHN IM 2000 28955.

Description: Shell minute, opaque, thick, height to 0.64 mm, width to 0.34 mm, with about three convex whorls and deeply impressed suture. Protoconch turbiniform, with ca. 1 ¼ whorls, diameter 156 µm, height of exposed part 164 µm. Protoconch sculpture of five strong, smooth spiral cords; interspaces as broad as cords and bearing minute, regularly spaced axial riblets narrower than their interspaces and not continued over the spiral cords. Protoconch terminated by a smooth, elevated varix. Teleoconch with slightly less than two convex whorls, with strong, smooth, prosocline axial ribs, extending over entire whorl, as broad as their interspaces which are smooth except for growth lines. Axial ribs ca. 14 on each whorl, last two preceding aperture attenuated. Periphery of teleoconch whorls slightly flattened, giving weakly biangulate profile. Umbilicus moderate to broad, with axial ribs becoming attenuated inside. Aperture oval to subcircular; peristome continuous, smooth inside, not thickened with respect to the preceding part. Animal and operculum unknown.

Species comparisons: Prior to the work of STEPHENS & VAFIADIS (2017), *Scalaro-*

noba was only known from New Zealand and included two extant species, *Scalaronoba costata* Powell, 1927 (type species by original designation) and *S. secunda* Powell, 1940, and two Miocene fossil species, *S. pristina* Laws, 1941 and *S. chemnitzia* Laws, 1944. The Australian *S. arenula* Stephens & Vafiadis, 2017 and *S. kryptopleurakia* Stephens & Vafiadis, 2017 complete the list of six currently accepted species of this genus. Of those, *S. costata* and *S. arenula* most resemble *S. madeirensis* n. sp. but, in addition to being separated by an enormous geographic gap, show conchological differences. *Scalaronoba costata* is more elongate in shape (height/width ratio ca. 1.8 vs. 1.5 in *S. madeirensis* n. sp.), the ribs fade out abapically on the last whorl and there is no umbilicus (vs. ribs continued into the umbilicus); *S. arenula* has one more cord on the protoconch and the edge of the protoconch is almost flush with the beginning of the teleoconch (vs. delimited by an elevated varix) and its umbilicus is a mere chink (vs. moderate to broad). The other Australasian species have definite knobs on the ribs which make a clearcut difference.

Figure 1. *Scalaronoba madeirensis* n. sp., A: holotype, from off Desertas, R/V Jean Charcot “Zarco” sta. 46, 100-130 m (height 0.61 mm); B: protoconch of the holotype; C: Paratype, same locality (height 0.60 mm)

Figura 1. Scalaronoba madeirensis n. sp., A: holotipo, frente a Desertas, B/O Jean Charcot “Zarco” sta. 46, 100-130 m (altura 0,61 mm); B: protoconcha del holotipo; C: paratipo, misma localidad (altura 0,60 mm)

The Italian Pliocene fossil *Camporellina mica* Bertosaso & Palazzi, 1997, albeit described in a different genus (but see discussion below), needs also be compared. It shares with *Scalaronoba madeirensis* n. sp. the minute size, solidity, and main aspects of the sculpture

but profile of the shell is narrower, the ribs on the teleoconch are fewer and have two distinct swellings separated by thinner (“saddle shaped” in the words of BERTOLASO & PALAZZI) intervals (vs. ribs of uniform thickness, narrowing only towards the umbilicus).

DISCUSSION

The current allocation of *Scalaronoba* to Eulimidae (MOLLUSCABASE EDS., 2025) results from a series of independent taxonomic allocations. PONDER (1967: 220–221), the only author to provide details on the soft parts in this genus, noted that *S. secunda* had a simple horny operculum, apparently no radula, eyes towards the inner side of the broad and flattened cephalic tentacles, no gill pinnules, and an ‘inrolled’ apex, concluding that it belonged in Pyramidellidae Gray, 1840 – a classification that was accepted by POWELL (1979: 267–268).

Subsequently, PONDER (1985: 106) transferred *Scalaronoba* to the family Aclididae (which at that time included

the heterobranchs *Cima* and *Graphis*) based on “re-examination of the shell” and a close resemblance to *Coenaculum Iredale*, 1924. The type species *Coenaculum minutulum* (Tate & May, 1900) is an elongate, multispiral shell with also coarse spiral cords on the protoconch and coarse axial ribs on the teleoconch that terminate above a basal spiral rib.

WARÉN (1993) separated *Cima* and *Graphis* from Aclididae, noting their Heterobranch features, and erected the family Cimidae, which included also *Coenaculum*, but *Scalaronoba* was not assessed and therefore remained in the Aclididae. Finally, BOUCHET *ET AL.* (2017) subsumed Aclididae within Eulimidae on the basis of Takano & Kano

(unpublished data) where Aclididae are nested within Eulimidae in a phylogenetic hypothesis based on DNA sequence data. Therefore, it was never proposed that *Scalargonoba* is an eulimid and this placement is only the result of its former placement in the Aclididae s.l. later united with Eulimidae. Instead, considering the original rationale of its similarity with *Coenaculum*, *Scalargonoba* should follow *Coenaculum* and be placed in the Cimidae. The protoconch is rather unique and does not qualify as heterostrophic, but Ponder's (1967) observation of "eyes towards the inner side of the broad and flattened cephalic tentacles" unambiguously qualifies *Scalargonoba* as an heterobranch, even making the initial choice of Pyramidellidae not unlikely.

BERTOLASO & PALAZZI (1997) reported for the first time the occurrence in Europe of a species resembling *Scalargonoba*, erected the genus *Camporellina* for their new species described from the Pliocene of northern Italy (province of Parma), and placed it tentatively in Aclididae together with *Coenaculum* and *Scalargonoba* (therefore ignoring Warén's instatement of Cimidae as separate from Aclididae). In their words, *Scalargonoba* differs from *Camporellina* by its circular peristome (ovate, slightly angulate at anterior and posterior end in *Camporellina*) and its rounded axial ribs (with two distinct swellings separated by "saddle like" depressions in *Camporellina*). Comparing the illustrations in BERTOLASO & PALAZZI (1997) with those of *Scalargonoba costata* (type species) and *S. secunda* in STEPHENS & VAFIADIS (2017), I can see no grounds for this genus level distinction. The aperture is broken on the illustrated specimens of *Camporellina mica* but is no less "ovate" and "angulose posteriorly" than in the type species of *Scalargonoba* (see STEPHENS & VAFIADIS, 2017 fig. 1 A-C), and the shape of the ribs is similar to *S. secunda*, therefore a species-level diagnostic character. The similarity in other quite unusual shell characters such as the

minute size and protoconch with strong spirals and terminated by a strong varix, support treating the Italian Pliocene fossil species as *Scalargonoba mica* (Bertolaso & Palazzi, 1997) n. comb.

How *Scalargonoba* arrived in Madeira remains a mystery. The morphology of the larval shell, with hardly more than one whorl with a thick wall and varix, suggests direct development and precludes dispersal with planktonic larvae. However rafting is a common alternative to larval dispersal (MARTEL & CHIA, 1991) and it has been proved at least in one instance that such minute shells can be suspended in the water column, possibly aided by mucus threads. WARÉN (1992: 166) reported a living *Anekes paucistriata* Warén, 1992 captured in a plankton net about 170 m above the seabottom, around Gorringe Bank. A distribution comprising continental margin locations and the Canaries, Madeira, and/or NE Atlantic seamounts is reported for other minute gastropods (e.g. *Anekes paucistriata*, *Lissotesta gittenbergeri* (Van Aartsen & Bogi, 1988), *Lissotesta turrita* (Gaglioli, 1987), *Cima minima* (Jeffreys, 1884), *Orbitestella dariae* (Liuzzi & Zucchi Stolfa, 1979) in a similar depth interval. Nevertheless, rafting could explain reaching Madeira from the African mainland or the Caribbean, not from the Pacific Ocean. The link between the Atlantic and European Cenozoic basins with Australasia needs to be more ancient, possibly going back to times of the Tethys Ocean and paralleling the history of *Posidonia* seagrasses.

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